

MSI Journal of Economics and Business Management (MSIJEBM)

Frequency:- Monthly Published by MSI Publishers

ISSN:- 3049-141X (Online)

Journal Link:- <https://msipublishers.com/msijebm/>

Volume:- 2, *Issue:-* 2 (February-2025)

Article History

Received on :- 07-02-2025

Accepted on :- 18-02-2025

Published on :- 21-02-2025

Total Page:- 10-20

DOI:-

Analysis of the Impact of Financial Inclusion on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria

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Abstract: This study examines the impact of financial inclusion on the performance, productivity, and sustainability of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in rural areas of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), Abuja, Nigeria. Using logistic regression analysis, the study finds that financial services significantly enhance SME performance, with an odds ratio of 1.379, and boost productivity and sustainability with odds ratios of 159 and 0.65, respectively. Each result is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating a strong positive relationship between access to finance and SME success in rural FCT. These findings underscore the vital role of financial inclusion in supporting rural SME growth and resilience. Recommendations include expanding financial services access, implementing financial literacy programs, and promoting digital finance solutions to address specific challenges faced by rural SMEs. This study highlights the importance of inclusive financial policies for fostering economic development and strengthening SMEs in underserved areas.

Keywords: Financial Inclusion, Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

1.0 Introduction

Given the important role that SMEs play in job creation and economic growth, research on financial inclusion and SMEs in rural regions is crucial (Magaji, Musa & Yusuf, 2022). According to Musa, Salisu, and Magaji (2024), financial inclusion is the availability and use of financial services by people and companies who are normally underserved or shut out of the official financial system. In rural contexts, where SMEs often face unique challenges, financial inclusion can be a catalyst for growth, innovation, and sustainability (Lu, Wu, Li & Nguyen, 2021).

Limited access to financial resources is a common characteristic of Nigerian rural SMEs, impeding their capacity to adopt new technologies, invest in expansion prospects, and effectively compete in the market (El-Yaqub & Ismail, 2025). Because financial institutions typically consider SMEs as high-risk, studies have indicated that access to financing is a major obstacle to the formation and expansion of SMEs in rural areas (Manzoor, Wei & Sahito, 2021). Due to this impression, rural SMEs receive less finance than their urban counterparts, resulting in a lopsided allocation of credit (Peón & Guntín, 2021). In addition to hindering these companies' expansion, a shortage of funding also reduces their ability to support local economies and create jobs (El-Yaqub, Ismail & Bappayo, 2024; Gombarume, 2014).

Furthermore, it is impossible to overestimate the contribution that government assistance makes to improving financial inclusion for rural SMEs. It has been demonstrated that government interventions to increase access to financing, like loan guarantees and microfinance programs, have a favorable effect on the performance of rural SMEs (El-Yaqub, Ismail & Eke, 2024). Financial institutions may be encouraged to lend to smaller businesses by these programs, which can assist reduce the risks involved in doing so. The ability of rural SMEs to efficiently use financial resources can also be improved by the provision of non-financial support, such as training and capacity-building initiatives (Ogujiuba, Olamide, Agholor, Boshoff & Semosa, 2022).

According to Magaji and Abubakar (2011), a key element in advancing financial inclusion among rural SMEs is the incorporation of technology into financial services. These businesses now find it simpler to manage their finances, access financial services, and conduct e-commerce thanks to the introduction of digital payment systems and mobile banking (Development of E-commerce and Innovation of Rural Small and Medium Enterprises, Magaji, Musa, Ahmed & Eke, 2024). However, the

availability of sufficient digital infrastructure in rural areas is a prerequisite for these technologies' efficacy. According to studies, rural SMEs must increase their digital literacy and internet connectivity in order to fully benefit from financial inclusion (Tiwasang & Sawang, 2021).

Moreover, there is a complicated and nuanced relationship between financial inclusion and the general performance of rural SMEs. By allowing SMEs to invest in necessary resources like inventory, equipment, and skilled staff, financial access can improve business performance. Increased competitiveness and productivity may follow from this (Manzoor et al., 2021). Nonetheless, SME owners' financial literacy is equally crucial since it affects their capacity to efficiently manage their resources and make well-informed financial decisions (Maziriri, Mapuranga, & Madinga, 2018). Therefore, attempts to increase rural SMEs' access to financing should be accompanied by programs targeted at enhancing financial literacy.

Furthermore, the financial environment for SMEs is significantly shaped by the socioeconomic background of rural areas. The success of financial inclusion programs can be greatly impacted by elements including educational attainment, societal perceptions of entrepreneurship, and the accessibility of local markets (Şerefoğlu & Gokkaya, 2017). For example, rural SMEs frequently function in areas with a high prevalence of informal lending practices, which can make the shift to formal financial institutions difficult (Peón & Guntín, 2021). Designing successful financial inclusion programs that address the particular requirements of rural SMEs requires an understanding of these contextual elements.

2.0 Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Financial Inclusion

According to Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2018), financial inclusion is the availability and accessibility of financial services, including banking, credit, insurance, and payment systems, to all people and enterprises, with a focus on low-income and marginalized groups. By empowering people to save, invest, and manage financial risks, it is crucial for advancing economic development, lowering poverty, and supporting inclusive growth (Sarma & Pais, 2011). Key elements that promote financial inclusion include microfinance organizations, digital banking, mobile payment systems, and laws that improve financial literacy and access (Allen et al., 2016). Despite

its advantages, its efficacy is hampered in many emerging nations by issues like poor financial infrastructure, regulatory constraints, and insufficient financial literacy (Ozili, 2020). Technological innovation, institutional reforms, and policy interventions targeted at closing gaps in financial access are all necessary to improve financial inclusion (Beck, 2016).

2.1.2 Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

In a variety of industries, small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) are essential to economic expansion, job creation, and innovation (Magaji, Musa & Ahmad & Eke, 2024). Although definitions differ by nation and industry, SMEs are generally defined by their lower workforce, revenue, and capital investment in comparison to major firms (OECD, 2021). These businesses boost market competitiveness, encourage entrepreneurship, and make a substantial contribution to national GDPs (Ayyagari, Demirgüç-Kunt, & Maksimovic, 2014). However, SMEs frequently encounter obstacles such as restricted financial access, legal restrictions, and roadblocks to technology adoption (Beck & Demirgüç-Kunt, 2006). Recognizing the critical role SMEs play in sustainable economic growth, governments and financial institutions around the world establish policies and support programs to encourage SME development (World Bank, 2020).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Finance-growth Theory

According to the finance-growth hypothesis, financial development plays a key role in promoting economic growth by enabling investment, capital accumulation, and effective resource allocation (Schumpeter, 1911). According to this hypothesis, healthy markets and financial institutions increase productivity through lowering transaction costs, enhancing risk management, and extending credit (Levine, 1997). Long-term economic growth and the expansion of the financial sector are positively correlated, according to empirical research, highlighting the function of financial intermediaries in promoting savings and financing innovation (King & Levine, 1993). A balanced approach to financial regulation is necessary, according to some academics, who contend that over-financialization can cause instability and crises (Arcand, Berkes, & Panizza, 2015). While recognizing the possible risks connected with financial expansion, the finance-growth hypothesis emphasizes the role that financial systems play in promoting economic advancement.

2.3 Empirical Review

Pradhan and Dahal (2021) investigated the connection between Nepal's financial inclusion and electronic banking. To determine respondents' opinions on electronic banking and financial inclusion, the study used primary data sources. The study tool was a structured questionnaire, and regression models were used to analyze the results. The study's conclusions showed that financial inclusion and a variety of electronic banking techniques were positively correlated. More automated

teller machines (ATMs) specifically had a positive effect on financial inclusion, suggesting that their growth boosted financial inclusion. The study also showed that greater financial inclusion was associated with a greater emphasis on mobile banking. The study also demonstrated the beneficial effects of online banking on financial inclusion, indicating that increased focus on online banking services enhanced financial inclusion. Additionally, it was discovered that agency banking positively impacted financial inclusion, suggesting that higher financial inclusion was correlated with more agency banking services. Finally, there was a positive correlation between financial inclusion and point-of-sale services, indicating that a stronger focus on these services led to a higher level of financial inclusion.

El-Yaqub, Musa, and Ismail (2024) use autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) as a methodology to examine how monetary policy affected economic growth in Nigeria between 1986 and 2021. According to the study's findings, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bound co-integration was used to evaluate the monetary policy's short- and long-term effects on Nigeria's economic growth. The results showed a long-term link. Further estimation results showed that monetary policy had an effect on Nigeria's economic growth. According to the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) conclusion, LM2 and LEXC have a somewhat bigger impact on GDP growth over a shorter period of time than INT and LBCP. Likewise, over a longer time frame, LM2 and LEXC significantly outperform INT and LBCP in terms of GDP growth. The analysis of the findings showed that the Central Bank of Nigeria's monetary policy actions had a significant impact on the nation's economic expansion. The Central Bank of Nigeria should therefore remove restrictions on lending to the private sector, which can boost an economy. Monetary policies should be utilized to encourage both local and foreign investment by encouraging the development of market-based interest rate and currency rate regimes.

Understanding how exchange rate variations affect export quantities and values is the main goal of Ismail, Musa, and Magaji's (2024) investigation into the effect of currency rates on Nigeria's export performance from 2010 to 2023. To determine the connection between Nigeria's export performance and currency rates, the study employed quantitative data analysis. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletins provided the study's data. The results show that from 2010 to 2023, the Nigerian Naira steadily increased in value relative to the US dollar, indicating very stable exchange rates during that time. Despite domestic obstacles like infrastructural and regulatory concerns as well as worldwide economic swings, Nigeria's export industry shown resilience with a general upward trend in export volumes and values. Strong positive relationships between export values and exchange rates (NGN/USD) were found using regression and correlation analysis, indicating a linkage between higher exchange rates and higher export earnings. But there are other important aspects as well, like domestic policies, commodity prices, and worldwide demand. Nonetheless, the report suggested that Nigerian policymakers give priority to

trade and exchange rate management strategies that increase Nigeria's export competitiveness and foster sustainable economic growth.

Bayar, Gavriletea, and Paun (2021) investigated the impact of internet and mobile phone use on financial inclusion using empirical data from post-communist EU nations. From 1996 to 2017, they used a panel study of cointegration and causality to gather sample data from 11 post-Communist European Union nations. First, they looked into whether access to financial institutions is impacted by the quantity of mobile phone contracts and Internet usage rates. They also examined how these factors affected financial market accessibility. According to the findings, mobile banking improves access to financial markets in Bulgaria, Croatia, and Hungary's rice fields as well as financial institutions in nations including Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, and Slovenia. Additionally, there was a negative correlation between mobile phone contracts and Czech financial institution access, as well as a correlation between Czech financial market access and Polish financial market access. The findings also indicate that access to financial markets and financial institutions and Internet usage have both positive and negative relationships. Internet use is directly linked to financial institutions in Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Hungary, and Poland, according to the study's findings, and it also enhances access to financial markets in Latvia and Slovenia.

Fernandes, Borges, and Caiado (2021) used an Automated Distributed Latency (ARDL) model to examine how digital financial services contribute to financial inclusion in Mozambique between January 2011 and September 2019. The study employed two models to examine how digital financial services contribute to Mozambique's financial inclusion as indicated by the country's bank account count. Traditional digital payment methods such automated teller machines (ATMs), point of sale (POS), interbank and interbank electronic money transfers, direct debit, and domestic and international remittances are used as independent variables in the first model.

Iwedi, Kocha, and Wike (2022) investigated how the Nigerian economy was affected by the digitization of financial services. In order to determine the relevance of the relationship between digital banking channels and Nigeria's economic performance, their study used 12 years' worth of annual aggregate data on digital banking from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. Multiple regression analysis was used. The results showed that Nigeria's economic growth was strongly correlated with both web and mobile payments. This suggests that Nigeria's economic expansion is closely linked to the digitization of banking networks. The authors draw the conclusion that digital banking is becoming more and more popular among Nigerian customers.

Oyelami, Adebayo, and Adekunle (2020) look into the factors that influence the adoption of electronic payments, how they affect consumers' decisions to buy, and how they affect the development of consumer spending in Nigeria. Both primary and secondary data

were employed in the investigation. Both descriptive (frequency and percentage) and inferential (Pearson correlation, hierarchical regression analysis, and analysis of variance) statistics were used to analyze the data that was obtained. The findings showed that the adoption of electronic payments in Nigeria is positively correlated with the determinants of electronic payment systems (convenience, security and safety, trust, and social influence). More than half (3/5) of the factors influencing Nigerian consumers' adoption of electronic payments were explained by these variables. The estimations' findings indicate that a number of important variables influence Nigeria's adoption of electronic payments, including income level, financial inclusion, educational attainment, and the availability of internet services and other financial infrastructures like mobile banking and point-of-sale devices. The findings also show that electronic payments have an impact on customers' decisions to buy, which raises consumer spending in Nigeria.

Financial inclusion in the era of digital banking: Lessons from rural India was studied by Cnaan, Scott, Heist, and Moodithaya (2023). Data for the study was gathered through focus groups and interviews. In seven Indian states, 3,159 households in villages were surveyed for the study. They looked at a cashless hamlet in each state as well as a comparator village close by. Given that there was little to no financial inclusion through digital banking, their findings imply that the comparator villages performed similarly to the cashless villages. They discovered that, in addition to notable state differences, the best indicators of engaging in any digital banking activity were financial literacy and internet access. The study's conclusion cautions against hastening the adoption of digital banking and cashless societies since underprivileged groups might be left behind.

2.4 Gap in the Literature

Although there is a wealth of information in the literature on the connection between financial inclusion and the growth of SMEs, nothing is known about how it specifically affects rural SMEs in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Although previous research has looked at the role that financial inclusion plays in economic growth and SME operations in general, little of it has addressed the particular difficulties that rural SMEs confront, especially when it comes to obtaining and using digital and financial banking services. Furthermore, there is not enough attention paid to the performance of microfinance institutions in the rural environment of FCT, Abuja, where access to traditional banking is limited, even though their importance in promoting the growth of SMEs is acknowledged. Furthermore, even though digital financial services are recognized as being essential to financial inclusion, it is still uncertain how applicable they are in rural areas with limited technology and infrastructure resources. In order to guide focused policy interventions, more research is required to examine how financial inclusion initiatives—in particular, digital banking and microfinance—affect the viability and expansion of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study looks at how financial inclusion affects small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) in Abuja's rural FCT. To gather data, the study used a survey approach and a structured questionnaire. Descriptive quantitative research employs this design. Since a descriptive quantitative research approach uses mathematics and calculation, it is frequently thought to be more accurate or useful than qualitative research, which focuses on gathering non-numerical data. This demonstrates even more how appropriate it was to use a descriptive quantitative research approach for this investigation.

3.2 Population of Study

All small and medium-sized businesses in the rural areas of the six local government area councils make up the study's population. The study uses a sampling strategy to help determine the population and sample size because the exact population of SMEs in the six local governments is not available.

3.3 Sampling and Sampling techniques

The sample size was chosen using straightforward and proportionate stratified random sampling procedures. Using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique, managers and owners of SMEs in rural areas were randomly selected from each of the six Local Government Area councils based on the size of their respective populations. The formula was as follows: Sample size of the strata = Size of entire sample/Population size x Layer size. Ultimately, 120 were chosen at random to participate in the study.

3.4 Method of Data collection

Questionnaires will be used to gather primary data. A yes-or-no-ended questionnaire is the one that should be used. Since the Yes/No closed-ended questionnaire is a dependable tool for gathering data and producing trustworthy analysis, it will be employed. The purpose of the research instrument was to answer research questions and provide answers pertaining to the particular study objectives.

3.5 Method of Data Analysis

Multinomial logistic regression techniques are used to analyze the data collected for this investigation. Although there are many more complex forms, multinomial logistic regression is a statistical model that uses a logistic function to model a binary dependent variable in its most basic form. One kind of regression analysis used to estimate the parameters of a logistic model—a kind of binary regression—is multinomial logit regression. The dependent variable in a binary logistic model, which logically has two possible values, such as pass/fail, is represented by an indicator variable with the labels "0" and "1". For the value "1" in the logistic model, the log-odds (the logarithm of the odds) is a linear combination of one or more independent variables (sometimes called "predictors"); these independent variables can be binary (two classes, coded by an indicator variable) or

continuous (any real value). The function that converts log-odds to probability is known as the logistic function. A value labeled "1" may have an associated probability that falls between 0 (certainly the value "0") and 1 (definitely the value "1"). The logit is the unit of measurement for the log-odds scale since the logistic unit is the source of the alternative names.

3.6 Justification of Method

The logistic model's limited predictive probability, which ranges from 0 to 1, served as the rationale for selecting the Multinomial Logit method as the estimate methodology. It is employed to simulate the likelihood that a particular class or event—such as pass/fail, profit/loss, win/lose, alive/dead, or healthy/ill—will occur. This may be expanded to simulate a variety of event classes, including figuring out whether an image shows a profit, loss, breakeven point, etc. A probability between 0 and 1 would be given to each object found in the picture, adding up to 1. Dichotomous outcome variables are modeled using the multinomial logit model. The logit model uses a linear combination of the predictor variables to model the outcome's log probability. These characteristics guarantee sound inference, effective conclusions, and recommendations that aren't deceptive. SPSS will be used to estimate the multinomial logit model for the given model. Predicted probability, goodness of fit, Nagelkerke [Pseudo R2], and the Omnibus test are used to assess the estimated model. These statistics allow us to determine the model's dependability and soundness.

3.8 Model Specification

In their article "Using Multinomial Logistic Regression to examined Financial inclusion in the digital banking age: Lessons from rural India," Cnaan, Scott, Heist, and Moodithaya (2023) used a model that was modified for this study. The logit model's implicit form is described as follows:

$$Z_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{ik} + u_i \dots\dots\dots (1) \text{Where:}$$

Z_i = SMEs Sustainability (dummy, 1= SMEs Sustainability and 0, otherwise). β_0 = constant

β_1 = coefficient

x_{ik} = set of explanatory variables ($i=1,2,\dots,k$) u_i = random error disturbance term.

The explicit form of the model is specified as:

$$Z_i = \ln P_i \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

$$1 - P_i$$

The Model is given as:

$$L = \frac{\ln(P)}{\ln(1-P)} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 AFS + \mu$$

Where: =

$L = 1$, if Access to financial services has any impact on SMEs sustainability in FCT, Abuja; $(1-P)$, if otherwise.

AFS = Access to financial

β_0 = The model's constant explains the relationship between SMEs' sustainability and a unit increase in each financial inclusion metric.

β_1 - β_3 = Coefficients of the independent variables μ = Error Term

Because it allows for a logical interpretation and accommodates a large number of variables, the multinomial binary logistic model was selected. The research sought to determine significant factors influencing a decision with a binary outcome, and in addition to its mathematical computational simplicity, the ordinary least square (OLS) technique was not appropriate for estimating the model because the dependent variable was binary.

3.9 Estimation and Evaluation Techniques and Procedures

Ominivous Test: It informs us of the general acceptability of the model. P-value is what we're talking about. It can be concluded that the model fits the data well if the P-value is less than 0.05. The null hypothesis in this case is that the model does not fit well. Whether or not the general model is acceptable will be determined here.

Goodness of fit: This is the percentage of the value that was accurately anticipated. This statistic will demonstrate the independent variables' explanatory power, or whether each one of them significantly contributes to the explanation of changes in the dependent variables.

Odd Ratio: This is the probability that something will happen. It illustrates how a predictor X consistently affects the probability that a particular event will transpire. Another name for it is the logit model's relative risk. It calculates the likelihood that $y=1$ is greater than the likelihood that $y=0$. The likelihood of $y=1$ occurring is twice that of $y=0$ when the odd ratio is 2. An odd ratio of 1 indicates equal likelihood, >1 indicates a higher likelihood of $y=1$, and <1 indicates $y=0$.

Nagelkerke R-Squared: It is an adaptation of the R-squared for Cox and Snell. Because it has an upper bound of one (1) and a bottom bound of zero (0), it is the most acceptable of the pseudo R-squared. It describes how the predictors in a model account for variations in the dependent variable.

Predictive Probability: Following model estimation, we use their functional form to forecast the likelihood that $y=1$ for every observation. This guarantees that the model will make accurate predictions.

$$P = \text{pr}[y=1/x] = F(x'\beta)$$

The range of the expected probability is 0 to 1. The chance of $y=1$ is shown by the anticipated probability.

Hypothesis Test: $H_0: \beta_0 = 0$ (the parameter estimate is statistically significant)

$H_1: \beta_0 \neq 0$ (the parameter estimate is not statistically significant)

Decision Rule: For p values >0.05 reject H_0

The likelihood of each parameter's predictive capability and statistical significance will be the basis for the judgment that determines whether any of the aforementioned hypotheses are accepted or rejected. Using the two-tail test, we reject the null hypothesis if the p-value is more than 0.05; if not, we accept it. We reject the null hypothesis for p-values <0.05 if the computed value is smaller than the value listed in the normal distribution table; if not, we accept the null hypothesis. We can forecast that $y=1$ if the expected probability denotes the likelihood of $y=1$, and $y=0$ otherwise if the predicted probability is less than 0.05.

4.0 Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Results

4.1 Data Presentation

The summary of surveys that were distributed and collected is shown in the tables below.

Table 1: Summary of Questionnaire Administration
Case Processing Summary

	N	Marginal Percentage
0	3	2.9%
Financial Inclusion	100	97.1%
1		
FEMALE	84	81.6%
GENDER		
MALE	19	18.4%
18-24	33	32.0%
25-34	32	31.1%
31-40	1	1.0%
AGE	32	31.1%
35-44	1	1.0%
41-50	4	3.9%
45- Above	5	4.9%
Divorced		
Married		
Single		
BSC/HND		
Academic qualification	71	68.9%
NCE/OND		

O'Level	27	26.2%
Valid Missing	8	7.8%
Total	63	61.2%
Subpopulation	32	31.1%
	103	100.0%
	0	
	0	
	94 ^a	

a. There is only one value for the dependent variable in 92 (97.9%) of the subpopulations.

One hundred and twenty questionnaires were distributed. 95.8% of the surveys were completed by the 115 that were collected from responders. The respondents failed to return five questionnaires. Twelve surveys were excluded from the analysis because they were deemed to be outliers. Only 103 of the 120 questionnaires that were sent ultimately made it into the final analysis, accounting for 85.8% of the total. Therefore, 85.8% is a sufficient representation of the entire sample and, consequently, the entire population.

The aforementioned data indicates that the majority of respondents are female, with 81.6% of respondents being

female and 18.4% being male. Additionally, it reveals that 32.0% of respondents are between the ages of 18 and 24, 31.1% are between the ages of 25 and 34, 28.3% are between the ages of 35 and 44, and 3.9% are beyond the age of 45. This distribution demonstrates that the study sample is between the young and the adult demographics. Comparably, the data reveals that 38.1% of respondents are single, 7.9% are divorced, and 54% of respondents are married. However, this indicates that married people make up the majority of entrepreneurs since they are thought to be more responsible and mature. Additionally, it reveals that 59.2% of respondents possess an NCE or OND, 8.3% hold a B.Sc. or HND, 5% hold another qualification, and 27.5% hold an O'Level.

Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	Df	Sig.
Intercept	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
Performance of SMEs	12.852	1.624	1	.203
Productivity of SMEs	11.659	.431	1	.511
Sustainability of SMEs	11.235	.007	1	.933
GENDER	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
AGE	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
Marital Status	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
Academic qualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER * AGE	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER * Marital Status	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER *				
Academic qualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
AGE * Marital Status	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
AGE *				
Academic qualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
Marital Status *				
Academic qualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER * AGE *				
Marital Status	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.

GENDER * AGE * Academicqualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER * MaritalStatus * Academicqualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
AGE * MaritalStatus * Academicqualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.
GENDER * AGE * MaritalStatus * Academicqualification	11.228 ^a	.000	0	.

The difference in -2 log-likelihoods between the final model and a reduced model is known as the chi-square statistic. By leaving off an effect from the final model, the reduced model is created. All of the effect's parameters being zero is the null hypothesis.

a. Since eliminating the impact does not result in an increase in the number of degrees of freedom, this reduced model is equal to the final model.

4.2 Data Analysis

Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria	Likelihood Tests			Ratio
		-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	
Intercept Only	23.545				
Final	11.228	12.317	34	.000	

Goodness-of-Fit

	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Pearson	8.984	59	.000
Deviance	8.220	59	.000

Analysis for Hypothesis One

Parameter Estimates

Financial Service	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Intercept	-9.445	4.978	3.600	1	.058			
Performance of SMEs	1.372	1.062	1.669	1	.003	3.944	.492	31.624

a. The reference category is: 1.

According to the results of the logistic regression, financial services have a 1.379 chance of affecting the performance of SMEs in the rural FCT of Abuja. Financial

services have a favorable and substantial impact on the performance of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja, according to the significant value, which is less than 0.05.

Pseudo R-Square

Cox and Snell	.001
Nagelkerke	.001
McFadden	.000

The most popular technique for assessing overall model fit in multinomial logistic regression is the likelihood ratio test, which is simply the chi-square difference between the null model (i.e., with the constant only) and the model with the predictors. Under Model Summary, we can see that the -2 Log Likelihood statistics are 60.570. It shows how poorly the model predicts pupils' academic development in ok status; the lower the value, the better the model.

Although they are not exact equivalents, the Cox and Snell or Nagelkerke statistic in logistic regression is comparable to the coefficient of determination in linear regression. A rough estimate of the coefficient of determination is given in the model summary.

Cox and Snell's coefficient of determination makes an effort to mimic several likelihood-based coefficients of determination. According to the Cox and Snell coefficient of determination, the predictor variable accounts for 51% of the variation in the dependent variable, which is thought to be sufficient.

Analysis for Hypothesis Two

Financial Services ^a	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Intercept	-3.820	2.321	2.708	1	.100			
Productivity of SMEs	.079	.562	.020	1	.001	1.082	.360	3.256

a. The reference category is: 1.

Similarly, financial services have a 159 percent chance of affecting SMEs' production in rural FCT, Abuja, according to the logistic regression result. Financial services have a

favorable and substantial impact on the productivity of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja, according to the significant value, which is less than 0.05.

Analysis for Hypothesis Three

Access to Finance ^a	B	Std. Error	Wald	df	Sig.	Exp(B)	Confidence Interval for Exp(B)	
							Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Intercept	-4.565	2.464	3.432	1	.064			
Sustainability of SMEs	.274	.599	.210	1	.001	1.316	.406	4.260

a. The reference category is: 1.

Finally, the results of the logistic regression indicate that the sustainability of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja, is more likely to be impacted by access to financing by 065. The fact that the significant value is less than 0.05 suggests that the sustainability of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja, is positively and significantly impacted by access to financing.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

The results of the logistic regression study demonstrate how important financial services are to improving the performance of SMEs in Abuja's rural FCT. A significant value below 0.05 suggests that financial service availability has a greater chance of having a favorable effect on SME performance, with an odds ratio of 1.379. This implies that SMEs are better equipped to enhance their company results when they have access to financial services like credit, savings, or loans. The favorable correlation emphasizes how crucial finance accessibility is to enabling small firms to expand and thrive in difficult rural settings.

Financial services have a significant impact on the productivity of SMEs in this area in addition to their performance. The p-value below 0.05 confirms the significance of the logistic regression finding, which indicates a remarkable possibility of a 159-fold increase in productivity for SMEs who use financial services. This implies that financial services play a crucial role in assisting SMEs in raising their productivity, operational effectiveness, and potentially innovative potential. Financial services help rural SMEs become more resilient and competitive by increasing production, which eventually supports overall economic growth.

Lastly, with an odds ratio of 0.65 and a significance level below 0.05, the logistic regression results show that financing availability has a favorable effect on the sustainability of SMEs in rural FCT, Abuja. This suggests that SMEs are better equipped to sustain operations, withstand economic ups and downs, and make long-term growth plans when they have easier access to capital. In this regard, SMEs must be sustainable in order to continue being viable contributors to the local economy and to lessen the vulnerability of rural communities that depend on their products and services.

5.0 Conclusion and Recommendations

According to the study's findings, financial inclusion is essential for SMEs' resilience and growth in rural FCT, Abuja, greatly improving their sustainability, productivity, and performance. By having access to financial services like lending, savings, and other resources, SMEs may plan for long-term survival, increase their efficiency, and overcome typical operational obstacles. These results highlight the significance of encouraging inclusive financial policies and increasing access to financial services in rural regions, as these actions are critical to supporting the health of rural businesses that support local communities and the overall economy and to promoting economic development.

To improve SMEs' access to financing in remote areas Policymakers, financial institutions, and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) in Abuja should increase access to customized financial services like microcredit and low-interest loans. To teach SME owners about financial management and the advantages of financial services,

financial literacy initiatives should also be created. By lowering administrative obstacles, streamlining loan and insurance application procedures can further increase accessibility. Establishing a favorable financial environment requires cooperation between governmental entities, financial institutions, and SME support groups. To guarantee the success of financial inclusion programs, policies should also address important issues including high transaction costs and inadequate infrastructure. Last but not least, encouraging digital finance options like online payments and mobile banking can aid in closing the gap in financial access in rural regions with weak banking systems.

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